

SOCIAL SCIENCES. Education & Educational Research

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Preparation of Future Specialists of the Social Sphere for the Formation of a Healthy Lifestyle of Pupils in the Professionally-Directed Educational Environment

Author's Contribution:

- A – Study design;
 B – Data collection;
 C – Statistical analysis;
 D – Data interpretation;
 E – Manuscript preparation;
 F – Literature search;
 G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:
Abstract

Preparing future social pedagogues and social workers for prevention activities with students in general and forming healthy lifestyles in particular is an important task of modern professional education of social specialists.

The aim of the study: to determine the effectiveness of the impact of the developed scientific and methodological support of the process of training future specialists in the social sphere to form a healthy lifestyle of students on indicators of their personal and professional potential.

Material and Methods:

The following complex of theoretical research methods has been used: analysis, comparison, generalization, systematization literature and interpretation of results. Methods of mathematical statistics have been used. The use of the Pearson criterion χ^2 in the statistical processing of experimental data in groups E_1 and K_1 (students of H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University) allowed to determine a significant difference in the readiness of future specialists of the control and experimental groups after the experiment and to prove the effectiveness of the experimental work.

Results:

The article revealed the components of the process of professional training of future specialists in the social sphere to work on the formation of healthy lifestyles of students, as well as the peculiarities of its organization in the various social institutions that carry out the function of preventing their maladjustment.

Conclusions:

The analysis of the results of the experimental study on the problem of preparing future specialists in the social sphere to form a healthy lifestyle of pupils allowed to draw the conclusions about efficiency of an experimental study on the formation of health-saving readiness of future social pedagogues and social workers in the conditions of state and non-governmental social institutions of the network of social care institutions affiliated with Higher Education Institutions.

Keywords:

professional training, future specialists in the social sphere, prevention of maladjustment of students, forming a healthy lifestyle, professionally-oriented educational space, social institutions.

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Introduction

Given the proliferation of aggression, bullying, various addictions in the environment of children and young people, the problem of preventing maladjustment of students in recent years has become extremely urgent, which necessitates the active search for effective ways to prepare future professionals in the social sphere to form a healthy social life of students. Preparing future social pedagogues and social workers for preventative activities with students in general and shaping healthy lifestyles in particular is an important task of modern professional education for social specialists, so it needs to take into account the requirements of the present (formation of humanistic orientation of actions and professional behavior, decisions, readiness to work in crisis situations, etc) during its implementation.

The realization of the above requirements is possible during the organization of the process of professional training of future social pedagogues and social workers in the conditions of professionally-oriented educational space, which provides conditions for conducting training sessions, practices and student scientific researches at the institutions of higher education and institutions partnering with it, that conduct work on prevention of maladjustment of students.

The analysis of the scientific literature showed that the researchers studied the following aspects of the problem of professional training of future social pedagogues and social workers to prevent maladjustment of students: features of interaction of social pedagogues with older adolescents who are prone to manifestations of addictive behavior; the formation of healthy lifestyles of students; technological and methodological support for the prevention and correction of adolescent addictive behavior in the work of social pedagogues of different social institutions; formation of specialists' readiness for preventive work with high school students; preparation of future social pedagogues and social workers for preventive work with students with deviant behavior; preparation of future social pedagogues for preventive activity in educational and training institutions. However, despite the great variety of research works, the problem of training future specialists in the social sphere to form a healthy lifestyle students under partnership of different social institutions is underdeveloped, lacks its scientific and methodological support, which would fully ensure professional self-determination and self-improvement of future specialists in the indicated direction.

The aim of the study. To determine the effectiveness of the impact of the developed scientific and methodological support of the process of preparation of future specialists in the social sphere for the prevention of maladjustment of students, the introduction of which allowed to develop a special professional competence to form a healthy lifestyle of students in the conditions of created professionally-oriented educational space, on the indicators of their professional personal potential.

The objectives of the article are: characterization of the components of content and features of preparation of future social pedagogues and social workers to work on the formation of healthy lifestyles of students in different social institutions as a basis for preventing their

maladjustment, as well as an experimental study of the impact of the developed methodological support on the indicators of their personal and professional potential.

Materials and Methods

The following complex of theoretical research methods has been used: analysis, comparison, generalization, systematization literature and interpretation of results. Methods of mathematical statistics have been used. The use of the Pearson criterion χ^2 in the statistical processing of experimental data in groups of students of H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University allowed to determine a significant difference in the readiness of future specialists of the control and experimental groups after the experiment and to prove the effectiveness of the experimental work.

Analyzing and summarizing the results of research and teaching practice has made it possible to argue that the role of social institutions in preventing the phenomenon of social maladjustment of students is crucial, so preparing future professionals in the social sphere to perform a preventive function is an important task of professional education. So, Lodkina (2009) proposes the introduction of schools of socio-ecological approach, which provides three areas: childhood ecology, family ecology and society ecology – which allows to create an educational environment that provides priority to the values of life, health and development of the child. The scientist notes that among the leading directions in work with children are: identification of children in the risk zone, identification of causes that lead to child maladjustment, as well as prevention in them of manifestations of deviant behavior, formation in students need for a healthy lifestyle (Lodkina, 2009, p. 82).

An important aspect in preparing future professionals in the social sphere for the prevention of maladjustment of students is to study the characteristics of psychological characteristics of children and young people who are prone to manifestations of deviant behavior. Thus, Malykhina (2012, p. 46) states that when looking for ways to prevent adolescent immoral acts, it is important to “pay attention to the individual, in all the variety of characteristics”. The scientist has determined the general psychological conditions for preventing immoral acts that affect the effectiveness of the entire educational process with adolescents in school (Malykhina, 2012, p. 89): timely diagnosis of immoral behavior of adolescents; formation of consciousness and self-consciousness, which determines the correct attitude to moral norms; development of a positive motivations and needs sphere of adolescent personality; establishing a trusting relationship between the caregiver and the pupil.

Based on the ideas of the aforementioned scientists, we introduced a supplement to the content of the training of future specialists in the social sphere during the acquisition of the special course “Social work on forming a healthy lifestyle”, which allows to increase the indicators of their personal and professional potential regarding the basics of diagnosing problems and difficulties of socialization of children and youth that lead to the development of maladjustment, by getting acquainted with the methods of creating and

using in the work of a social pedagogue of the general secondary education institution a student "health passport" and methods of formation of healthy lifestyles in terms of various social institutions.

Researchers have shown that the occurrence of various deviations in students' behavior is much easier to predict and create conditions for their avoidance than to later make efforts to correct them. Thus, Korchova (2007, pp. 48–49) developed a structural-logical model of prevention of sexual deviance of high school students, which reflects the system of preventive work, which is a specific subsystem in the general system of school work. The scientist argues the need for the formation of sexual culture of high school students (Korchova, 2007, pp. 55–58), which contains the following components (cognitive: knowledge of the basics of a healthy lifestyle, the idea of human sexuality; emotional-volitional: willingness to master inter-gender skills, behavioral: compliance with the rules and rules of sexual culture). The researcher defined the following criteria (physiological culture, psychological culture, ethical culture, social culture) and indicators (physical development, awareness of sexual physiological functions of the human body, abandonment of bad habits; correspondence of sexual life to actual age, formation of morally-acceptable intercourse between sexes, the formation and priority of human values, the presence of a positive ideal, the understanding of socially-acceptance forms of sexual relations, formed social responsibility, responsible attitude for the destiny of another person, formed vision of the future family) formation of high-value social motives of high school students, aimed at preserving and strengthening the sexual culture, self-education skills, positive moral attributes.

The researcher also determined the conditions that ensure the effectiveness of the school of formation of sexual culture of high school students (Korchova, 2007, pp. 137–138): improving the quality of upbringing and education of high school students, taking into account their individual and age characteristics of psychosocial development and use of educational interactive technologies; providing pedagogical personnel with the latest pedagogical technologies, forms and methods of forming the sexual culture of high school students, introducing them into the practice of comprehensive educational institutions; organization of purposeful scientific and practical work with parents through psychological-communicative trainings, discussions, lectures, role-playing games, problem seminars, seminars-workshops using interactive forms and teaching methods; formation of high-motivated high school students for healthy lifestyle and sexual culture. Considering the above conditions in the preparation of future social pedagogues will allow timely detection and prevention of the spread of sexual deviance among students.

The influence of social and pedagogical activity on educational, physical cultural and healthy work on the formation of the health culture of schoolchildrens and students was studied by Melnyk (2017, 2019).

Fetisova (2014) proposes to use the following preventive tools for the work of a social pedagogue with

"difficult children" who have suicidal tendencies: trainings to get out of difficult life situations, identify abilities and interests, communicate with teenagers about plans for the future, etc. We consider it necessary to familiarize future social pedagogues and social workers with the peculiarities of using the above-mentioned means in preventive work with students who are prone to suicidal behavior, which will improve their professional health-saving competence.

One of the important problems in the work of social workers is prevention of child neglect in Ukraine. Orzhekhovskaya (2009, p. 6) identifies the following strategic directions of its decision: 1) creation of such preventive space for the child and such educational system at school, which would prevent alienation of pupils from the educational institution, ensure a positive microclimate in the school teams, facilitate the acquisition of specific preventive methods by subject teachers, classroom leaders, deputy directors of educational work, school psychologists, social pedagogues; the need to consolidate the efforts of the school, law enforcement agencies, NGOs, religious denominations, work with parents; 2) implementation of measures to adapt and re-socialize street children by introducing ... alternative forms of education and upbringing ... maximizing the use of social rehabilitation schools; 3) providing training for the prevention of child neglect.

Analysis of the research of Ternovets (2013, pp. 50–52) showed that among the effective forms of preparation of future social pedagogues for the prevention of social orphanage in school the following were identified: workshop "Creating a data bank of innovative social and pedagogical experience", video lectures "Modern pedagogical technologies to prevent the emergence of social orphans", trainings "Psychology of pedagogical communication" (for social pedagogues); research work (participation in conferences, olympiads, competitions of student scientific works, projects, grants of the Department of Social Pedagogy of Shevchenko LNU), talks, consultations, round tables, etc (for future social pedagogues). Given the above ideas of researchers, it is important in the preparation of future social pedagogues and social workers to create conditions for organizing continuous interaction of social work students with pupils deprived of parental care and prone to vagrancy, who are the pupils of specialized institutions (psychologists, social rehabilitation centers working with young people who are addicted to narcotic substances, etc) during the acquisition of variant special courses, training and on-site practice during 3-5 years of study and participation in research.

As Kyrychenko and Kovganich (2009, p. 7) point out, "the attribute of an innovative educational institution of the 21st century becomes an educational space that is opened, aimed at fostering a child as a subject of one's own life and success, and mastering one's vital competence". Researchers define the principle of "preventive" as one of the leading principles of construction of educational space (transformation of risk environment into space of opportunities for self-realization of a child's personality makes it possible to significantly increase the efficiency of educational

work, to prevent the spread of negative phenomena in the child and youth environment) (Kyrychenko & Kovganich, 2009, p. 9). Scientists have identified the following methodological tools that will allow to solve effectively the problems of educational space (Kyrychenko & Kovganich, 2009, pp. 10–11): reorganized councils of student self-government; special subjects or elective courses that promote self-development of the individual; an extensive network of circles and clubs for the sake of pre-vocational training and vocational guidance; children's and youth non-governmental organizations. The use of the ideas of Kyrychenko and Kovganich (2009) in the professional training of future specialists in the social sphere made it possible to substantiate the need to form their willingness to organize complex health-saving activities at all levels of interaction of specialists in the environment of a certain social institution: in the context of student self-government and social services, in terms of professional interaction with parents and students, in terms of professional interaction with colleagues from different social institutions and during scientific research. Analysis and generalization of the results of the research by Pykhtina and Novhorodskyi (2007, p. 11) allowed to identify groups of children who are prone to maladjustment: school-age children not attending school; orphans; socially-orphaned children; adolescents using drugs and toxic substances; adolescents with sexually explicit behavior; teenage offenders. We consider it necessary to acquaint future specialists in the social sphere with the above-mentioned classification of pupils in order to determine the features of preventive work with vulnerable categories of student youth.

Among the important directions of early prevention of social and pedagogical neglect of the child, the researchers identify the following (Pykhtina & Novhorodskyi, 2007, pp. 20–25): 1) humanization of the educational process through the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational environment developing healthy lifestyle values; expansion of leisure activities; creation and introduction of technologies of early diagnostics of various forms of deviant behavior); 2) improving family relationships through outreach to parents, working with families at risk); 3) assisting the individual in self-improvement and self-realization through preventive training and education.

Familiarization of future specialists in the social sphere with the abovementioned conditions, which provide full socialization and individualization of the child's personality, will allow to carry out preventive activities in the educational environment comprehensively and to ensure the elimination of negative factors at different levels (personal, micro-environment and environment). To carry out prevention activities with students, Pykhtina and Novhorodskyi (2007, pp. 170–171) propose to use a model that combines four components of the pedagogical model of prevention: 1) information; 2) education; 3) an alternative that will allow us to form an adequate self-esteem and feel useful in society; 4) interventions (specialist consultations, helpline, peer coaching, creation of new communication groups, etc).

We consider it necessary to acquaint future professionals in the social sphere who carry out preventive work with students, with the proposed model during the acquisition of the special course “Designing social and educational environment”, which will enhance their professional competence in this direction. Given that negative effects such as aggression and bullying have become widespread in the student environment, work to prevent child abuse is an important area of social work to prevent students from maladjustment. Analysis of the results of the research of Panchenko (2013) allowed to identify in the content of social and pedagogical work of general secondary education institutions and other social institutions three types of prevention of child abuse: primary (informing children and young people from prosperous families about legal norms and real life situations regarding abuse); secondary (group work with children, parents of “at-risk” families to build knowledge and life skills needed to protect against violence, as well as establishments that assist victims of violence through training, information, clarification, etc); tertiary (mainly provided in shelters, specialized institutions for children and young people, who are prone to risky behavior through consultations and peer and self-help groups). The researcher (Panchenko, 2013, pp. 42–46) also singled out the features and suggested different forms and methods of preventive work with parents, children, teachers and in the environment (lectures, parent universities, parental meetings, trainings, etc). Familiarization of future social pedagogues and social workers during the practice-oriented training on the basis of partnership with Higher Education Institutions network with the essence and peculiarities of work on the prevention of abuse of children ensures the acquisition by future specialists of special professional competence in the specified direction while studying subjects such as “Technology of social and pedagogical work”, “Technology of social work abroad”, “Social and rehabilitation work in specialized institutions”.

Training of future specialists in higher education institutions was studied by Melnyk and Pypenko (2018). An analysis of the results of Predborskaja's (2006, p. 15) research showed that “contemporary changing reality requires probabilistic thinking: the complication of things requires the complication of mental structures, which, in turn, implies corresponding changes in the content and methods of teaching”. Taking into account the ideas of the researcher, in the process of professional training of future specialists in the social sphere to work on the prevention of maladjustment of students during the mastering of the discipline “Ethnopedagogy” there were used innovative experience, new forms and methods of social work with vulnerable contingents in order to develop in students probabilistic thinking and the means to work in a changing world, to enable them to adapt professionally in their learning and professional development (Kostina, 2018b).

Analysis and synthesis of scientific studies on the philosophy of education showed that among the problems of modern professional education, scientists see the low level of general methodological training of future professionals and suggest introducing special

courses in philosophy of life to improve the characteristics of the pedagogical process (Korotiaiev, Kurylo, & Savchenko, 2010). To increase the level of preparedness of future specialists in the social sphere to work on the formation of healthy lifestyles of students, we introduce them to the philosophical foundations of health care activities as a basis for forming their professional outlook while mastering the discipline “Social work for preservation and promotion of health”.

Results

Based on the above ideas of scientists, with the aim of increasing the effectiveness of professional training of future social pedagogues and social workers to prevent maladjustment of students, the formation of their special competence to form a healthy lifestyle of students through the implementation of complex professional health saving activities of various specialists in the field of coordination of specialists in the system of various social institutions we have developed such scientific and methodological support (Kostina, 2016, 2017, 2018a, 2018b): training manual “Theory and Practice of Ethno-Pedagogical Means in Professional Training of Social Workers to Prevent Maladjustment of Students”, “Curricula and Methodological Support for Special Courses for Future Social Pedagogues and Social Workers”, “Designing a social and educational environment for students”, “Social work on forming a healthy lifestyle”, methodical materials to ensure the passage of social and pedagogical practice in the Institutions of Secondary Education and social services, the introduction of training “Professional skills of a specialist in the field of work with vulnerable contingents”, methodological materials for the preparation of scientific studies on social pedagogy and social work on the problem of prevention of maladjustment of students. With the introduction of the above-mentioned methodological support in the process of preparing future social pedagogues and social workers, an enriched professionally-oriented educational space was created, the presence of which made it possible to realize certain components that make up the content of professional readiness of future specialists in the social sphere to form a healthy lifestyle; locate student in the “risk zone”; identify the causes that lead to maladjustment of students; prevention of students’ divergent behaviors through multi-level and multi-directional activities to help students develop healthy lifestyle needs and develop healthy lifestyle skills.

In order to create a professionally-oriented educational space during the experimental study, cooperation agreements were concluded between H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University with Kharkov Pedagogical Lyceum No. 4, Kharkiv High School

No. 36, Kharkiv Gymnasium No. 43, Kharkiv Specialized School of I-III Grades No. 134 of Kharkiv City Council of Kharkiv Region, CSSFCY of Kyiv and Kholodnogorsk districts of Kharkiv, The Kharkiv Regional Center for Social and Psychological Rehabilitation of Children and the Municipal Community Center for Kharkiv Regional Center for Social and Psychological Rehabilitation of Children “Harmony”, by the Community Service and Social Services Charitable organization “Caritas-Kharkiv”, by “Kharkiv Charitable Foundation Blago”, Kharkiv Regional Public Organization “Culture of Health”, Sector of Juvenile Probation in Kharkiv, a branch of the State Institution “Probation Center” in Kharkiv region, which provided opportunities for professionalization of future social pedagogues and social workers of the experimental group in the direction of forming a healthy lifestyle of students during the organization of training sessions, educational events, practices and conducting scientific research on mentioned topics.

Future social pedagogues and social workers, during the experimental study, had the opportunity not only to get acquainted with the theoretical bases of health-saving activities with students, but also to learn the practice of preventive health-saving activities during direct interaction with leading specialists of the social sector and in different social institutions (general secondary education institutions, centers for social and psychological rehabilitation for children, CSSFCY, community organizations, etc). An important aspect of their professional training was learning the experience of partnerships between specialists of different social institutions in order to solve students’ problems and prevent their maladjustment (Kostina, 2018a, pp. 142–147). Among the interesting experiences of interaction with students belonging to vulnerable contingents, accumulated by future social pedagogues and social workers, it is worth mentioning the carrying out of educational activities for the formation of healthy way of life for students displaced from the ATO zone on the basis of COCF “Caritas-Kharkiv”, Republican prophylactic quest from COKhCF “Blago”, organization of preventive measures for children deprived of parental care, on the bases of centers for social and psychological rehabilitation of children and the sector of juvenile probation of the city of Kharkiv and others.

The analysis of the results of the experimental study revealed the positive dynamics of indicators of personal and professional potential of future specialists in the social sphere compared with the results of measurements in the control group (see Table 1), which allowed to confirm the effectiveness of the developed scientific and methodological support.

Table 1. Dynamics of formation of future social educators and social workers readiness for prevention of students’ maladaptation (%).

Levels of manifestation	The beginning of the experiment		End of experiment	
	E ₁	K ₁	E ₁	K ₁
Professionally specialized	0.0	0.0	31.6	10.5
Professionally qualified	26.3	31.6	42.1	31.6
Primary	39.5	57.9	26.3	57.9
Insufficient	34.2	10.5	0.0	0.0

Statistical processing of data using Pearson's criterion χ^2 to check the homogeneity of distribution between groups E_1 and K_1 after forming the experimental part

made it possible to determine that there is a statistical difference between samples E_1 and K_1 , which is evidence of its effectiveness (see Table 2).

Table 2. Statistical verification of experimental study results using the Pearson criterion χ^2 .

Groups		P-value before experiment	Statistical difference between groups	P-value after experiment	Statistical difference between groups
E	K				
E_1	K_1	6.271 < 7.378	Absent	9.071 > 7.378	Exists

Discussion

The analysis of scientific researches on the problem of professional training of future social pedagogues and social workers for the prevention of students' maladjustment showed that the following ideas were offered by scientists: creation of conditions for development of skills and abilities for preventive work in the child and youth environment (Fetisova, 2014; Korchova, 2007; Lodkina, 2009; Malykhina, 2012; Melnyk, 2017, 2019; Panchenko, 2013; Pykhtina & Novhorodskiy, 2007; Ternovets, 2013); formation in future specialists of philosophical basis for effective realization of future professional activity (Korotiaiev, Kurylo, & Savchenko, 2009; Kyrychenko & Kovhanych, 2010; Melnyk & Pypenko, 2018; Predborskaja, 2006). The conducted researches have allowed to confirm the importance of the ideas proposed by the author regarding the influence of the developed professional and educational environment on the indicators of the personal and professional potential of future social pedagogues and social workers.

Conclusions

The analysis of the results of the experimental study on the problem of preparing future specialists in the social sphere to form a healthy lifestyle of pupils allowed to draw the following conclusions: 1) programs of professional disciplines and programs of practice of students of 1-6 years of study with questions concerning preservation and promotion of health of pupils; introduction of the training "Professional skills of a specialist in the field of work with vulnerable contingents"; development and implementation of a special course "Social work on forming a healthy lifestyle"; 2) increasing motivation and interest in the prevention of students' maladjustment in the course of scientific research and in volunteer initiatives on the basis of a network of social assistance institutions partnering with the HEI; 3) the use of the Pearson criterion χ^2 in the statistical processing of experimental data in groups E_1 and K_1 , allowed to determine a significant difference in the readiness of future specialists of the control and experimental groups after the experiment and to prove the effectiveness of the experimental work.

A promising direction for further research is to identify opportunities to use the developed scientific and methodological support for training social professionals to form a healthy lifestyle of pupils in the system of further professional development of social sphere specialists and in training volunteers.

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